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“HE BUILT VOICES WHILE MISPLACING HIS OWN”

I've been in love with chalk that scrapes the green surface slow
Those pieces of paper kept a scent I've known for years
A taste of joy returns when greetings come and softly grow
With gratitude that lingers long, dissolving through my tears

This was always a dream I've longed to hold within my hands
Was this an ambition mine, or only borrowed from their name?
Something irreversible still moves beneath these shifting sands
Am I lost in sadness or in light, are both the same?

I always kept the fire burning
As I cross paths of courses and topics
Assuring everybody gets what's planned in learning
Yes, I learn, but what fire lights a heart with unseen leaks?

I build personalities and values
I teach what I have learned for years in continuous
I construct emotions and knowledges from expected different human hues
But, what about me, why lost in blues

Hey, Dear Me!
You've been doing good, why now this pause?
Are we lost in the middle of emptiness,
Or has the point not yet been reached, so these feelings arise?

Those were sometimes; I don't regret what I become
But I still search for where I went in all this
If I was ever really whole on my own
Or just someone built in the act of service

One day I might finally see

Why giving so much felt like becoming the less of me
Why every voice I helped grow and always stand
Took pieces of mine I didn't plan

So, if my voice feels distant in the noise they keep
Know that I'm still here, just buried under ground deep
Still learning how to come back to my own name
After building so many other the same.

